

1 **A regulator of HIV-1 mRNAs.**

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8 A Prp19-associated complex contains CRNK1, a reported binding partner of HIV-1 mRNAs. We studied
9 total transcription by RNA-sequencing in cells engineered to lack CRNK1 to understand the molecular
10 basis of Crnk1 function in mRNA biology. Crnk1 controlled host of small nucleolar RNAs or SNORAs.
11 Crnk1 appeared to function at least in part by interaction of control of other nuclear factors with functions
12 in RNA or DNA binding, including the polypyrimidine tract binding protein 2 or *Ptbp2*, the transcription
13 factor *Yy2*, the arginine and serine rich protein *Rsrp1*, and *Smcr8*. CRNK1 controlled the expression of a
14 gene known as cardiomyopathy associated 5, or *Cmya5*.

15 Citations

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GSE144347